

Kinetics and Mechanism of Chloraminometric Reactions involving some Primary Alcohols

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Kinetics of oxidation of some primary alcohols viz. *n*-butanol, *iso*-butanol and *iso*-pentanol by chloramine-T in acidic media has been reported. A first order dependence in each chloramine-T and hydrogen ion and a zero order dependence in alcohol has been observed. No effect of ionic strength was evident. A plausible mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed. Various Arrhenius parameters have been computed. Corresponding aldehydes have been found to be the reaction products.

THE study of oxidation mechanism of alcohols has been an interesting problem since long time.

Kinetic investigations regarding the oxidative processes involving alcohols and various oxidising agents have been reported by many workers¹⁻⁵ and the various oxidants used were other than chloramine-T. The chloramine-T/toluene sulphonamide system has a high value of redox potential⁶ in both acidic (1.139V at *pH* = 0.65) and alkaline media (0.499V at *pH* = 12) and as such is a powerful oxidising agent and has, therefore, been widely used for the estimation of several organic and inorganic compounds⁷. Very little is known about the kinetics and mechanism of oxidations involving chloramine-T⁸⁻¹⁰. Recently, the kinetics and mechanism of chloraminometric processes involving various reducing substrates has been investigated by Mushran and coworkers¹¹⁻¹⁷

In the present communication, the kinetics of oxidation of some primary alcohols viz. *n*- and *iso*-butanol and *iso*-pentanol in acidic media (*pH* = 4.0 to 5.2) has been investigated. The main aim has been to explore the complete mechanism of the chloraminometric reactions

Experimental

Aqueous solutions of *n*- and *iso*-butanol and *iso*-pentanol (B.D.H., AnalaR grade) were prepared. All other solutions were prepared as mentioned in an earlier communication¹². Bidistilled water was employed for the preparation and dilution of the solutions. The kinetics was followed by estimating chloramine-T from aliquot portions of the reaction mixture withdrawn at definite interval of time, iodometrically,⁷ using starch as an indicator.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reactions was obtained by taking known excess of chloramine-T over al-

cohol to interact at *pH* = 4.5 and at 50° and this may be represented as follows :

where R represents $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_2$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH.CH}_2$ for *n*-butanol, *iso*-butanol and *iso*-pentanol respectively. Corresponding aldehyde was found as one of the reaction products, which was confirmed by positive spot tests.¹⁸

Results

Kinetics of oxidation of above mentioned alcohols by chloramine-T was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. First order dependence in chloramine-T was followed at all concentrations of the reactants. Pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) in chloramine-T, calculated from the slope of the linear log-time plots, were independent of the alcohol concentration (Table 1), establishing a zero order dependence of the reaction rate with respect to the reducing substrate

***pH* dependence :** Reactions rates for the oxidation of alcohols by chloramine-T were highly susceptible to the change in the *pH* of the reaction mixture. Kinetic investigations were carried out at different *pH* and the results are presented through a linear plot of $\log k_1$ vs *pH* (Fig. 1). The slope of the straight line is found to be -1, establishing a first order dependence in hydrogen ion concentration.

Ionic strength effect : The effect of the change of the ionic strength of the media ($\text{NaClO}_4 = 0.1$ to 0.4 M and KCl and $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.1$ to 0.8 M) on reaction rate was found to be negligible.

Temperature dependence : The influence of the temperature on the first order rate constants was investigated in the temperature range 45°-60° and

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT'S CONCENTRATION

10 ³ [Chloramine-T] M	10 ² [Alcohol] M	$k_1 \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of					
		<i>n</i> -butanol ^a		<i>iso</i> -butanol ^b		<i>iso</i> -pentanol ^b	
		45°	50°	45°	50°	45°	50°
0.5	2.0	2.28	3.87	2.73	3.92	2.72	4.15
1.0	2.0	2.28	3.77	2.53	3.86	2.56	4.01
2.0	2.0	2.24	3.55	2.31	3.48	2.16	3.43
3.0	2.0	1.94	3.23	2.01	3.13	1.96	3.00
1.0	1.0	2.30	3.77	2.53	3.92	2.56	4.01
1.0	3.0	2.28	3.83	2.58	3.96	2.60	4.03
1.0	4.0	2.30	3.87	2.56	3.94	2.58	4.01

^a at pH = 4.4; ^b at pH = 4.0

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs pH, [Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Alcohol] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ at 50° for the oxidation of *n*-butanol, *iso*-butanol and *iso*-pentanol in A, B and C respectively

the values of the various Arrhenius parameters were computed and are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS

Alcohol	E $k \text{ cal mole}^{-1}$	A $1 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	ΔS e.u.
<i>n</i> -butanol	13.7	1.63×10^9	-17.5
<i>iso</i> -butanol	14.8	3.29×10^9	-16.0
<i>iso</i> -pentanol	15.6	1.30×10^{10}	-13.3

Discussion

Chloramine-T (CAT) in aqueous media behaves like a strong electrolyte and is freely ionized into (CAT⁻) and Na⁺. The anion of chloramine-T, in acidic media undergoes protonation to give the free acid, *p*-toluenesulphochloramide (CAT') which on hydrolysis^{11,19} gives toluenesulphonamide (TSA) and hypochlorous acid as shown in steps (3) and (4).

Thus an acidic solution of chloramine-T contains CAT⁻, CAT' and HOCl and one of these three can react with the alcohol in a fast step as the rate is independent of the concentration of alcohol.

It is therefore, clear that the overall rate is controlled by the rate of the formation of one of the oxidising species formed in the step (2), (3) or (4). From the experimental observations and from the earlier work of Soper²⁰, Higuchi and Hussain⁸, the rate is determined by the formation of HOCl (slow step 4) which would interact with the alcohol in a fast step.

Further it is seen from table 1 that an increase in initial concentration of chloramine-T results in a slight decrease in the first order rate constants. This may be explained as an inhibitory effect²¹ caused by the formation of small quantities of NaClO₃ in a side reaction¹² as shown in steps (5) and (6).

A general mechanism for the oxidation of primary alcohols by chloramine-T may thus be proposed as follows.

After applying steady state treatment with respect to CAT' and HOCl and making a reasonable approximation viz. $k_4\{k_{-2}+k_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]\}[\text{S}] \gg k_{-2}k_{-3}[\text{TSA}]$, the following rate law equation is obtained.

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}^-] = \frac{k_2k_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{k_{-2}+k_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [\text{CAT}^-][\text{H}^+] \quad (8)$$

In acidic media CAT^- may be taken as CAT and thus the equation (8) becomes

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CAT}] = k[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

where

$$k = \frac{k_2k_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{k_{-2}+k_3[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} = \text{constant}$$

The derived rate law equation (9) is in complete accordance with the experimental kinetic results.

Further, Soper and Smith have suggested²² that the rate of interaction between HOCl and alcohol is very fast in comparison to the rate of the interaction between CAT' and alcohol which is in agreement with the step (7).

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